

and roots) of *Salvia lanata* Roxb. was soxhletted with light petrol (b.p. 60-80°) and chloroform in succession for 48 h each. The residue from chloroform extract was chromatographed over silica gel, elution being carried out with solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarity.

The concentrate of light petrol-benzene (1 : 1) eluate-fractions afforded a solid crystallised from petroleum ether-benzene (3 : 1), m.p. 184-85°, [α]_D + 80° (CHCl₃). Its identity with α -amyrin was established by direct comparison (co-tlc, co-ir and m.m.p.) with an authentic sample⁵.

Further elution of the column with benzene furnished another triterpene having m.p. 233-34°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3300 cm⁻¹; m/z 442 (M⁺), 234, 207, 203, and 189. It was identified as uvaol by comparative studies (m.m.p., co-ir and co-tlc) with an authentic sample⁶ and through the preparation of acetate, m.p. 157°.

The fraction eluted with benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) yielded a solid which on repeated crystallisation from methanol furnished colourless solid, m.p. 270-72°; [α]_D + 80° (CHCl₃). It responded to Leibermann-Burchard† test for triterpene. The ir spectrum of the compound showed bands at $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1700 (carbonyl), 1695 (carbonyl) and 1640 cm⁻¹ (unsaturation); methyl ester, m.p. 190-92°. The mass spectrum of the compound registered the molecular ion peak at m/z 454 along with other significant peaks at m/z 248 (base peak), 205, 203 and 202.

Finally, the identity of this triterpene as ursonic acid has been confirmed by the usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic sample⁷.

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Chemical Investigation of the Whole Plant of *Erigeron canadensis*

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ERIGERON canadensis (Compositae) is known¹ to be used in diarrhea, dysentery, kidney affections etc. Bohlmann *et al*² isolated a cumulene derivative from the plant. The present investigation reports the isolation of a sterol mixture shown to be α -spinasterol (stigmasta-7,22-diene-3 β -ol) and stigmast-7-en-3 β -ol and a steroidal ketone mixture shown to be stigmasta-7,22-dien-3-one and stigmast-7-en-one.

Experimental

The plant material was collected during January to April from Burdwan district in West Bengal.

Extraction and Isolation of constituents: Dried and powdered whole plant of *E. canadensis* (2 kg) was extracted with light petrol (b.p. 60-80°) for 12 h in a soxhlet apparatus. Evaporation of the solvent yielded a crude extract (28 g), which on chromatography on a column of silica gel yielded two solids, Solid A (4 g), m.p. 168-170° as the less polar component, and Solid B (2 g), m.p. 164-166° as the more polar constituent.

Solid B: The physical properties of the more polar Solid B and its acetate were very close to those of α -spinasterol (stigmasta-7,22-dien-3 β -ol) and its acetate³. Solid B acetate does not depress the m.p. of α -spinasteryl acetate.

	M.p.	[α] _D
Solid B	164-166°	0°
Acetate	174-176°	0°
α -Spinasterol	170-172°	-4°
Acetate	175°	-3.5°

However, the mass spectrum of Solid B acetate (M⁺ 456 and 454) indicated⁴ it to be a mixture of the acetates of α -spinasterol and stigmast-7-en-3 β -ol. We failed to resolve the acetate mixture even on a column of silica gel impregnated with silver nitrate, but could chemically prove it to be a mixture of the above two compounds.

It is known⁵ that the Δ^{22} -double bond of α -spinasteryl acetate can be preferentially reduced on catalytic hydrogenation but the Δ^7 -double bond is simultaneously rearranged to $\Delta^{8(14)}$ -position to yield stigmast-8(14)-en-3 β -yl acetate and that stigmast-7-en-3 β -yl acetate rearranges⁶ to stigmast-8(14)-en-3 β -yl acetate under the same condition. Accordingly, the acetate of Solid B was shaken in

ether solution with Pd-charcoal in an atmosphere of hydrogen to yield a single compound, stigmast-8(14)-en-3 β -yl acetate, m.p. 115° (lit⁶ m.p. 115°) (Found: C, 81.36; H, 11.54. C₃₁H₄₈O₂ calcd. C, 81.52; H, 11.48%) [α]_D +20°; δ 2.03 (3H,s), 4.7 (1H,t) and no olefinic proton. *m/z* 456 (M⁺, 100%), 441, 396 and 381.

Solid A: Solid B on oxidation with chromium trioxide-pyridine complex⁷ yielded the less polar component Solid A, m.p. 168-170°; [α]_D +36.7° which was identical (m.m.p., tlc and ir) with a sample of Solid A from natural source. Hence Solid A was a mixture of stigmasta-7,22-dien-3-one⁸ and stigmast-7-en-3-one⁹.

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Spectrophotometric Study of Reaction Between Iron(III) and 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime

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SEVERAL oximes¹⁻¹¹ have been proposed for the colorimetric determination of iron(III), but in most of the cases the color was not stable for sufficiently longer periods because of the dissociation of the complexes. We have now found that 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime develops an intense forest-green color with iron(III) at pH 2.3-2.7 and the reaction is highly sensitive and selective. The

sensitivity according to Sandell's method¹² is 27.9 ng cm⁻², and as determined by Feigl's method¹³ the limits of identification and dilution are found to be 100 ng and 1.1 × 10⁶, respectively. The color is stable for about six hours and, therefore, a detailed spectrophotometric investigation of the complex was carried out.

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime was prepared according to the procedure described by Vogel¹⁴. Ferric alum (A.R., B.D.H.) was dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid and standardised by volumetric method¹⁵.

A Toshniwal CLO/O2A conductivity bridge, an Elico 820A pH meter and a Toshniwal RLO2 spectrophotometer were employed for conductance, pH and absorbance measurements, respectively.

Procedure: An aliquot of Fe^{III} solution containing not more than 24 ppm of iron was treated with 4 ml of 0.1 per cent solution of oxime at room temperature. The pH was adjusted to 2.5 and the volume made up to 50 ml. The absorbance of the iron complex was measured at 450 nm with the reagent of the same concentration as the blank. The concentration of iron was deduced from a standard calibration curve obtained under identical conditions.

Results and Discussion

Iron(III) complex exhibits maximum absorption at 450 nm at which the reagent, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime has no absorption. Any excess reagent has no effect on the absorbance of the complex. The complex obeys Beer's law in the range 6-24 ppm of iron(III). The sensitivity according to Sandell's definition is 27.9 ng cm⁻² at 450 nm for an absorbance of 0.001 with a molar absorptivity of 0.2 × 10³ l mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Job's method of continuous variation^{16,17}, slope ratio¹⁸, mole ratio¹⁹ and Asmus methods²⁰ showed that the ratio of metal to ligand in the complex is 1 : 1. The study of the isobestic point (Fig. 1) obtained by plotting the optical densities of the complex against the wavelength at various pH values (2.5-10.5) indicated that during the pH range 2.5-4.5 the absorption curves do not pass through the isobestic point and hence, a single complex was present, while an isobestic point exists in the pH 5.5-10.5 at a wavelength 415 nm and an optical density of 0.085 showing the presence of a mixture of complexes.

The iron-naphthaldoxime complex could be readily extracted into nitrobenzene. The conductance of pure nitrobenzene as well as the iron complex in this solvent was found to be 5 × 10⁻⁴ Ω⁻¹. This clearly shows that the complex is a non-electrolyte. One of the most conspicuous features of ferric iron in aqueous solution is its tendency to hydrolyse. In the pH range 2-3 iron may be present